

Table 2. Frequency of restorers, partial restorers, and maintainers for V20 A in red- and white-kernel rice varieties. Kerala, India. 1994-95.

Varietal group	Lines (no.)	Restorers	Partial restorers	Maintainers
Red kernel	17	0 (0) ^a	7 (41.2)	10 (58.8)
White kernel	21	6 (28.6)	8 (38.0)	7 (33.4)

^aFigures in parentheses indicate percentages.

IKI stain. Three panicles each from the same plant were bagged before flowering to facilitate selfing. Spikelet fertility was calculated as percentage of filled grains. Hybrids showing >80% pollen and spikelet fertility were classified as fertile, those with 100% pollen and spikelet sterility were considered sterile, and the rest were classified as partially fertile. Accordingly, the male

parents were classified as restorers, maintainers, and partial restorers (Tables 1 and 2). Among the 43 varieties tested, 18 were effective maintainers, 7 effective restorers, and 16 partial restorers. The response of two varieties depended on the female parent used (maintainer/restorer for one CMS line and partial restorer for the other), indicating the influence of the genetic background of

the female parent on the nuclear gene expression of the male parent. The frequency of main-tainers and partial restorers was very high among the red-kernel rice varieties, but practically nil among complete restorers. Hybrids with the red-kernel Kerala rice varieties when used as male parents were either sterile or partially fertile, but none was completely fertile. The sterile hybrids are being back-crossed with some of the identified maintainers (PTB39, PTB52, MO 4, MO 8, etc.) to develop locally adaptable CMS lines with red kernels for future use in hybrid rice development. The fertile hybrids are being assessed for their heterosis and adaptability under different conditions. ■

Machhapuchhre 3 (MP3), the first rice variety developed through a participatory plant breeding approach released for mid to high altitudes of Nepal

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Adoption rates for exotic rice varieties in the eastern and western hills of Nepal are reported to be 10-11%. Seven F₅ bulks representing three crosses—Fuji 102/CD, K332/NR10157-2B-2, and Stejaree 45/CD—were given to expert farmers identified through a village workshop. They were asked to grow and manage the new entries along with their local variety in the same way. The participatory plant breeding (PPB) system included a farm walk to different trial sites, preference ranking, measurement of farmers' managed yield data, postharvest evaluations by women farmers, and monitoring of varietal spread. Farmer-selected lines were also included in national yield trials to satisfy variety release require-

Comparison of the means of top five conventionally bred varieties (CBVs) with that of Machhapuchhre 3.

ments. In contrast to conventional breeding practices, most farmers grew the new entries in medium fertility conditions. A few farmers chose plots they regarded as problematic. The overall strategy emphasized risk aversion and expanding successful lines to better fields. Decisions on retaining or rejecting any rice entry was largely taken after women farmers thoroughly evaluated postharvest traits, such as white grain color along with aroma, softness of cooked rice, and ability to expand and remain dry after cooking. Focused group discussion with the farmers revealed that grain yield alone did not influence farmers' decision of adopting and spreading MP3 although the variety yielded well

even in the formal varietal trials (see figure). Machhapuchhre 3 has been officially released for altitudes between 1400 and 2000 m of western Nepal, on 14 Jul 1996, or less than 8 yr from the initial crossing in autumn 1988. This is the first recorded example of a successful variety developed by decentralized selection of segregating material through PPB drawing active participation of expert farmers. Experience from this experiment suggests that the PPB approach is a cost-effective and suitable method for developing farmers' need-based crop varieties. ■

Breeding of Z-Biao S line, the indica photothermosensitive genic male sterile line with recessive purple leaf maker

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We developed two photothermosensitive genic male sterile lines (PTGMS) with recessive purple leaf marker, Zi-Biao S-1 and Zi-Biao S-2, to eliminate seed contamination that may result from incomplete male sterility of PTGMS lines in a two-line, hybrid rice seed production system.

The Zi-Biao S lines are indica-type PTGMS lines derived from the cross between Tan-Zi, a purple-leaf indica rice variety, and 1356 S, an indica PTGMS line. These lines had slower critical sterility temperature than the parent lines. Under 14-h daylength and under controlled conditions, pollen sterility was more than 99.9% and seed

Table 1. Pollen sterility of Zi-Biao S lines under artificial climate chamber.

PTGMS	Stage of panicle development ^a	Daily mean temperature (°C)	Mean pollen sterility (%)
Zi-Biao S-1	III	24.07	99.99
	IV	24.07	99.99
	V	24.03	99.99
	VI	23.01	100.00
Zi-Biao S-2	III	24.00	99.99
	IV	23.01	99.99
	V	23.91	99.99
	VI	23.97	99.99

^a Treatment period was 4 d; sample size was 10 plants in each treatment.

Table 2. Main agronomic and outcrossing characters of Zi Biao S lines. Guizhou, China.

Line	Plant height (cm)	Panicles plant ⁻¹ (no.)	Spikelets panicle ⁻¹ (no.)	Grain weight (g)	Days to heading	Rice quality	Spikelets (%)	Exserted stigma (%)	Response to GA ₃	Angle of glume opening
Zi Biao S-1	59.7	7.5	113.6	23.0	85	Good	29.8	69.1	Sensitive	45°
Zi Biao S-2	55.8	7.0	129.0	23.0	94	Good	36.3	63.2	Sensitive	41°

set under bagging was zero (Table 1). Under natural photoperiod and temperatures in Guidion, Guizhou (26°35' N, elevation of 1006 m), the pollen sterility of plants which flowered from 18 Jul to 29 Aug was 100%, and the complete male sterile period was 43 d. Plants which flowered after 30 Aug reverted to fertility (pollen fertility ranged from 15 to 50%).

During the fertile period, seed setting was 21.4% in Zi-Biao S-1 and 54.1% in Zi-Biao S-2. The average temperatures in the first, second, and last 10 d were 22.0, 25.1, and 28.4 °C in Jul 1995 and 24.5, 23.5, and 25.3 °C in Aug 1995. The monthly average day-

length was 13.61 h in Jul 1995 and 13.02 h in Aug 1995.

Their agronomic characters and outcrossing traits were superior (Table 2). The presence of purple leaf at the seedling stage can be used as marker for eliminating selfed-seedlings of the PTGMS line in F₁, that result from incomplete male sterility of PTGMS line owing to consecutive lower temperatures (>4 d, <24 °C) in two-line hybrid seed production. Other rice varieties mixed inadvertently in multiplication of the PTGMS line can also be easily removed by using the purple leaf as a marker. Thus, these lines will be useful in maintaining the purity of hybrid crops. ■

High-frequency plant generation in wild species of *Oryza*

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We are developing a system for Plant regeneration from wild species of *Oryza*. In recent work, dehusked seeds were surface-sterilized with 0.1% (w/v) HgCl₂ solution for 5 min and rinsed four times in sterile distilled water. Sterilized seeds were kept for germination on MS medium devoid of growth hormones in light (1600 lux) at 25 °C. The endosperm and radicle were excised from 7-d-old seedlings, which were then inoculated on MS medium supplemented with 6.0 mg BAP L⁻¹. Multiple shoots or micropropagules developed at the base of shoots were used for callus initiation. Segments

(0.5-1.0 cm long) cut from their white tissue were inoculated on LS medium containing 2.5 mg 2,4-DL⁻¹, 3% sucrose, and pH was adjusted to 5.8. The cultures were kept in the light. Embryogenic calli from the primary cultures were subcultured on the same medium and then transferred to regeneration medium based on MS salts supplemented with 2.0 mg BAP L⁻¹ and 0.5 mg NAAL⁻¹. All media were solidified with phytigel (0.2% Sigma) and growth hormones avoided. Rooted plantlets were transferred to pots.

Callus induction was observed in all wild species. Normally, callus developed at both the nodal and internodal regions of the propagules (see figure, a). Induction frequency varied among species. An embryogenic type of calli—compact, globular, shiny, and white or pale yellow—developed in all the wild species, whereas both accessions of *O. meridionalis* produced fast-growing nonembryogenic calli. Plant regenera-

a. Callus development from nodal and internodal regions of the shoot bases of *O. nivara*. **b.** High-frequency plant regeneration in *O. nivara*. **c.** Rooting of regenerated plantlets derived from *O. nivara*. **d.** Field transfer of plantlets raised in vitro.

tion also varied among species (see table). Both accessions of *O. meridionalis* failed to regenerate into plantlets and